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MemMan: A Fortran and C++ Interoperable Memory Manager on Modern High-Performance Computing Platforms

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Abstract

In recent years, scientific High Performance Computing (HPC) software stacks are increasingly embracing C++ because of the extensive ecosystem and the superior GPU support across different vendors. However, many important applications are still written in Fortran. The weather and climate prediction model, ICON, for example, is written in Fortran and is still an operational model for daily weather forecasts for several countries. A Fortran code containing millions of lines of code, like ICON, cannot be easily rewritten in C++. The reasonable solution would be to rewrite components of the code in C++. However, there is no standard for cross-compiling Fortran and C++ code. Interfacing C++ and Fortran code is a tedious task. Cross-compiling can be error-prone because there is no proper compiler message or debugger for cross-compiling. For an alternative approach enabling coexistence and interplay of C++ and Fortran code, we developed a memory manager library, MemMan, which handles data passing between Fortran and C++ codes. MemMan simplifies Fortran-C++ interfacing by handling the argument passing in the library. MemMan manages not only CPU memories, but also GPU memories of different vendors. The memory manager library assists an incremental rewrite of large Fortran applications into C++. MemMan was motivated by the modernization effort of the ICON code, but it has been made general such that it works for all Fortran and C++ cross-compile applications using GPUs. With the help of MemMan, a Fortran application can easily try out

performance portability libraries such as Kokkos and numerical libraries such as Ginkgo.

CCS Concepts

• **Software and its engineering** → **Interoperability**; **Software evolution**; • **Information systems** → *Deduplication*.

Keywords

memory manager, Fortran-C++ interoperability, GPU, legacy code, cross-compilation

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1 Introduction

Many important HPC applications were written in Fortran. The K computer records 68% of their invocations to be Fortran [32] in 2014. The UK Archer supercomputer also reports Fortran as the main user language [29] in 2016. In 2018, NERSC still documents around 70% of users programming in Fortran on the Cori supercomputer [12], similar to the ratio of users programming in C++. However, in a 2022 survey [19] on the Exascale Computing Project, about 70 percent of the applications in the project were written in C++, compared to less than 10 percent in Fortran. We can observe a general trend that HPC software stacks are shifting from Fortran to C++. However, many legacy applications were initially written

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in Fortran, and rewriting these Fortran codes in C++ while keeping both the performance and the user base is not an easy task.

A key reason why developers prefer C++ over Fortran is that most supercomputers nowadays are not only equipped with GPUs, but also draw the lion’s share of their compute performance from the GPUs. In the top500 list published in June 2025 [9, 17], nine of the top ten supercomputers achieve their peak performance using GPUs, including GPUs from Nvidia, AMD, and Intel. Not only do GPUs become an important part in modern HPC, but interoperability has also become a critical concern in code development. To get the best performance on most supercomputers, one has to implement the same kernel in multiple APIs: CUDA for Nvidia GPUs, HIP for AMD GPUs, and SYCL for Intel GPUs.

In general, C/C++ has better GPU support compared to Fortran [20]. In the three main GPU ecosystems, only Nvidia provides an API for Fortran. There is no Fortran support for HIP and SYCL. OpenMP and OpenACC directives offer a way to outsource data-parallel computations to GPUs from Intel, AMD, and Nvidia, respectively, but there exists little flexibility for optimization using in-line pragma constructs. Performance portability programming models such as Kokkos [18, 28], RAJA [14], and ALPAKA [33] are all libraries based on C++. Thus, HPC researchers have largely moved their main programming language from Fortran to C/C++.

Translating existing legacy Fortran code into C++ is not a straightforward task. For example, ICON [23] has served as a weather and climate prediction model for more than 20 national weather forecast centers around the world. With a code base of 7,500 files and 2.3M lines of code, it is impractical to rewrite everything in C++ from scratch. Not to mention that the code is under active development and is used every day for weather prediction. Step-by-step re-implementation with cross-compilation is the solution to code rewrite of this scale. To cross-compile Fortran and C++ codes, we need a proper interfacing method and, more importantly, a mechanism for sharing data between the programming ecosystems.

Neither Fortran nor C++ is ABI (Application Binary Interface) compatible. However, both Fortran and C++ provide good interfacing methods for C. Thus, a natural workflow relies on the use of an intermediate C layer with which both languages can interface. In this paper, we will assume that a code component was reimplemented from Fortran to C++, and we want to call the C++ code from a Fortran driver program.

The data passing between Fortran and C++ is involved and requires careful consideration of several aspects. First, the memory address of the data should be passed correctly. Secondly, the data types have to match. Data types in Fortran must be transferred into C data types to be recognized by the interface functions. Moreover, scalar types in Fortran are passed by reference by default, which is different from C++, where scalar types are passed by copy by default. Reference data types cannot be passed into intrinsic data types. Third, when passing an array, one has to pass along its size and layout because Fortran arrays and C++ vectors are not interoperable. We should also consider that Fortran arrays are by default column-major, compared to C++, which has default arrays in row-major. The memory manager tool that we developed is a concept that solves all the inconsistencies of data in different languages.

In some detail, we develop a memory manager for data passing between Fortran, C, and C++. Our memory manager is motivated by

(a) Components required to interface between a Fortran subroutine and a C++ function (without MemMan).

(b) Components required to interface between a Fortran subroutine and a C++ function (with a memory manager).

Figure 1: Interfacing Fortran subroutines and C++ functions.

the ICON climate and weather prediction model, but it works for any applications that cross-compile Fortran and C++ code. Examples will be shown in section 6. It also adapts to the requirements in the ICON model, including enabling a complicated variable descriptor (not a simple string) for data. The feature of adding metadata in different types is also established in the memory manager. Our memory manager is implemented with a C++ backend to ensure memory safety. C and Fortran interfaces are built on top of the C++ memory manager backend.

2 Interoperability

Calling C++ functions from Fortran or Fortran subroutines from C++ is not a trivial task. Neither Fortran nor C++ has a standard application binary interface (ABI). However, Fortran can guarantee C interoperability by `bind(c)` and C++ by `extern "C"`. We find that the interoperability between Fortran and C++ through an intermediate C interface is the most reliable path.

While C++ compilers often follow a common ABI for symbol generation, the C++ standard itself does not define how those are generated. Most C++ compilers follow the Itanium C++ ABI standard [1], though they are not guaranteed to have the same representation. This issue is pointed out in a technical documentation by vendors [8]. As a result, cross-compiler compatibility and symbol linking would be compiler-dependent, making it risky to rely on C++ symbols when interfacing with other languages.

Figure 1a shows the standard required components of a Fortran-C++ interface. Due to the inconsistent ABI behavior, one needs to add a Fortran wrapper and a C interface to call a C++ function from a Fortran subroutine. In the Fortran wrapper, we convert the intrinsic Fortran types of the arguments to the ISO C binding types. In the C interface, we write a simple C function wrapped in the

```

example_externc.cpp
1 extern "C" {
2 void my_c_function_double(double* x, double* y) {
3     my_cpp_function<double>(x, y);
4 }
5 void my_c_function_float(float* x, float* y) {
6     my_cpp_function<float>(x, y);
7 }
8 }

```

Figure 2: An example code snippet for the C++-C interoperability.

`extern "C"` declaration, which calls the actual C++ function. The Fortran wrapper can be omitted if the Fortran subroutine already uses the ISO C binding type for its arguments. The C interface can be omitted if the C++ function is written in pure C symbols with pure C type arguments. In an ideal scenario, we will have a memory manager (MemMan) handling the data passing as shown in Figure 1b. The Fortran subroutine only needs to call the Fortran function of MemMan, and the C++ function only calls the C++ function of MemMan. The memory management and interfacing are handled by MemMan. Without passing data via function arguments, one can easily wrap the C++ function with a `extern "C"` declaration and call it from Fortran.

From a memory management perspective, we also need to handle all memory allocations in C++, because the C++ standard specifies that manipulating any data not recognized by the abstract machine leads to undefined behavior. Data managed by Fortran and passed to C++ might cause unexpected behaviors or runtime errors [2]. Conversely, data generated or managed by C++ is safe for C and Fortran. Allocating and managing memory in C++ ensures that we stay within the language’s guarantees, minimizing the risk of undefined behavior and ensuring safe interoperability across the different languages in use.

2.1 C++-C interoperability

C++-to-C interoperability is relatively easy because it can be achieved in a single file. A C++ function can be compatible with C ABI by wrapping the function with `extern "C"`. Figure 2 shows an example code making C-compatible functions in C++. Without the `extern "C"` declaration, each C++ compiler is not guaranteed to compile the function such that it can be called in C. The function and arguments also cannot contain any C++-specific features, such as templates and C++ standard libraries. As also shown in the example code, one needs to wrap a templated C++ function with a C interface.

2.2 Fortran-C interoperability

Fortran-C interoperability is more complicated because we need to write separate Fortran and C code in two files and do cross-compilation. Figure 3 shows a simple example of a Fortran-C interoperable function. The Fortran subroutine with a `bind(c)` attribute must have the same name and arguments as the corresponding C function.

```

example_bindc.f90
1 use iso_c_binding, only :: c_double
2 subroutine my_c_function(x, y) bind(c)
3     real(c_double) :: x, y
4 end subroutine

example_bindc.c
1 void my_c_function(double* x, double* y) {
2     // my implementation
3 }

```

Figure 3: An example code snippet for Fortran-C interoperability with `bind(c)`.

Matching the types of arguments is the primary challenge of a functional Fortran-C interface. First, one needs to use the Fortran types from the `iso_c_binding` to guarantee compatibility with the C types. For Fortran code that uses intrinsic data types, one has to write a wrapper code to convert the types to `iso_c_binding` types. Secondly, Fortran variables are passed by address by default. Passing a `c_double` variable in the Fortran argument means passing a `double *` pointer in C, as shown in Figure 3. Adding a value attribute in Fortran will match `double` type in C, but then creates a copy of the data. In this case, the data passing is only one direction. Thirdly, array types in Fortran and C do not match. One has to pass a pointer to the first element instead, and the size information of the array will be lost. The C descriptor is introduced in the Fortran 2018 standard to resolve this issue, which we will discuss in the next subsection. One can also pass the array as an extra argument. However, this can expand the argument list significantly.

The Fortran–C interface demands careful attention to ensure its correctness. One simple change in data type can result in code failure, and there is no standard way to debug cross-compilation code. The challenges for interfacing Fortran code to C/C++ led to the motivation of developing a memory manager for Fortran-C++ interoperability.

2.3 C descriptor (Fortran 2018)

The Fortran 2018 standard introduces the C descriptor (`CFI_cdest_c`) for better Fortran-C interoperability [25, 26]. Figure 4 is an example code snippet of a C-interoperable function using the C descriptor, compared to Figure 3, which shows a code snippet of simple `bind(c)` before Fortran 2018.

The C descriptor feature provides better interoperable support, especially for Fortran arrays. For example, one can pass assumed-rank Fortran arrays with the C descriptor. One can also request the array size, rank, and other information with the C descriptor saved in the `CFI_cdesc_t` struct. However, not all compilers support the C descriptor feature, and some compilers only support the C descriptor partially.

Within the major Fortran compilers, Flang does not yet have a version supporting C descriptors [5]. The GNU compiler only has more complete support since version 12.0 [4]. The NVHPC compiler first mentioned the Fortran 2018 C descriptor support in version 23.11 [3]. Both are relatively new versions. The incomplete

```

example_bindc.f90
1 subroutine my_c_function(x) bind(c)
2   real(c_double), allocatable :: x(:)
3 end subroutine

example_bindc.c
1 #include <ISO_Fortran_binding.h>
2 void my_c_function(CFI_cdesc_t *x) {
3   int status;
4   CFI_CDESC_T(1) array;
5   // establish a C descriptor array
6   status = CFI_establish((CFI_cdesc_t *)&array, ...);
7   // update the values
8   status = CFI_section((CFI_cdesc_t *)&array,
9                       (CFI_cdesc_t *)&x, ...);
10 }

```

Figure 4: An example code snippet for Fortran-C interoperability with C descriptor (Fortran 2018).

support on all compilers contradicts our goal of a Fortran-C++ interoperability solution across different platforms.

As a result, we refrained from using the C descriptor and instead opted for a more robust solution based on the older Fortran-C interface with `bind(c)`. It provides a stable, consistent mechanism for symbol generation that works reliably across compilers and platforms.

3 Memory Manager

3.1 Existing Technology

There are many existing memory manager libraries. However, to the best of our knowledge, none fits our purpose of providing a language-portable memory manager for both Fortran and C++ on GPUs. The Kokkos built-in memory manager `Kokkos::View` [28] handles memories both on CPUs and on GPUs. One can allocate data, copy the data from host to device, and device to host. The Kokkos view even handles data passing by default in simple GPU configuration settings. However, `Kokkos::View` does not support memory management in Fortran. `Memkind` [16] is a library that helps control memories of different kinds (CPU), including NUMA, DRAM, and HBM. `Memkind` does not support GPU memory management, nor does it have a Fortran interface. `Mosaic` [11] is a simulator that optimizes paging in GPUs depending on the application. `Umpire` [15], `Gallatin` [24], `XMalloc` [22], `ScatterAlloc` [27], `RegEff` [30], and `Ouroboros` [31] are libraries that handle GPU memory allocation, where `Umpire` supports not only NVIDIA, but also AMD GPUs.

To the best of our knowledge, there is yet no suitable library for managing CPU and GPU memories that can be used for both C++ and Fortran languages. Therefore, we developed this memory manager to bridge cross-compiled C++ and Fortran codes for computation on both the CPU and GPU.

Figure 5: The memory manager concept

3.2 Our solution (MemMan)

To ensure safe and efficient interoperability between Fortran and C++ within the ICON system, we developed a new memory manager that addresses the challenges of mixed-language HPC environments. The primary objectives of the memory manager are to (1) enable seamless data exchange between Fortran and C++, (2) ensure compatibility with modern HPC architectures, and (3) maintain backward compatibility with the existing Fortran-based codebase. These goals guided the design of a robust, portable memory management solution.

Our memory manager (MemMan) consists of three main parts: a memory-safe C++ backend, a C interoperability layer, and a Fortran interface for the user. MemMan is an open-source library maintained under the DKRZ-domain GitLab. Figure 5 shows the concept of our memory manager.

From a driver code, users can call functions in either Fortran or C++. Users can also call device kernels such as CUDA and Kokkos. Inside each component module (function or kernel), all data is requested from the memory manager. There is no need to pass data while interfacing Fortran and C++ codes. Launching a C++ function or kernel from Fortran only requires a dummy C interface, and vice versa. The user does not need to deal with complicated data passing and type matching like the traditional Fortran-C bindings.

3.2.1 Concept and Workflow. All data that will be passed between Fortran and C++ will first be registered and allocated in the memory manager. The data can then be accessed on demand from the memory manager via `find_data`. The driver code that calls functions and launches kernels can either be in Fortran or C++. Codes of a different language from the driver code only required a dummy C interface and do not need to pass data because all data is managed by the memory manager. See 3.2.2 for details on how this is achieved.

Register variables. A variable should be registered before access. MemMan registers a variable using a (variable) key. A key can be a simple string representing the name of a variable or a struct containing the variable name and some integers specifying the variable state or property, such as grid index and time index. We name these structs variable descriptors (`VarDescriptor`). `VarDescriptors` are very useful for applications such as climate simulations, where

the same property would have multiple states saved in separate memory positions.

Allocation. Allocation of data in MemMan is separated from the register function to provide a more flexible memory layout. A MemMan data is only created upon allocation. Therefore, the data is aligned by the order of allocation. The User can align variables to improve the cache behavior.

Variable descriptor. Users interact with MemMan using variable keys. A simple key can be a string describing the name of the variable. In MemMan, we have a built-in key struct `VarDescriptor`, which contains the variable name string and four integers describing the variable. The variable descriptor is inspired by the ICON legacy code, where programmers like to create derived types for variable names of physical properties. The extra integers can indicate position in space or time. In section 5, we will show that the `VarDescriptor` key does not add significant time to MemMan operations.

Data access. Users request data directly from the memory manager using the `find_data` function. Users pass the key and the device where the data is stored to MemMan. MemMan looks up the internal table for the requested data and returns the memory address to the user.

Metadata. Apart from the memory for the variables, MemMan also allows the user to save metadata for each variable. Common metadata includes the rank and size of the array. The rank and size are automatically saved as metadata when an array is registered in MemMan. The user does not have to register extra integers that describe the rank and sizes of an array.

3.2.2 C++ backend. MemMan follows several key design principles. All memory allocations are managed within C++, in accordance with the C++ standard that requires data manipulated by the C++ Abstract Machine to be allocated within the same environment to avoid undefined behavior. Fortran interacts with the memory manager through a lightweight C interface. This approach makes the extension for other programming language bindings similarly simple and uniform.

MemMan is composed of three main components: the global registry, the global index, and the registries. Each of these plays a critical role in MemMan. Figure 6 shows the structure of the three components.

Global registry. The global registry is an aggregate of all components in MemMan. It serves a similar role to the CUDA handle, which manages everything in MemMan. The global registry is a critical component for managing the scope of the memory manager. A unique pointer of the global registry will be created upon the first usage of any MemMan functionality. A user will then interact with the global registry to either add or get data from MemMan. The Fortran interface also interacts with the same global registry via the intermediate C layer. We detail this concept in 3.2.4.

Registry. A registry is where we actually store the data. A registry is created for each supported data type and for each device (CPU and GPUs). All data in a registry (same type and device) is created upon allocation. All variables are aligned densely in a vector by

Figure 6: The memory manager class structure

their allocation order, and can be accessed easily by knowing which element of the vector one requires.

Global index. The global index is an index table for all variables stored in MemMan. The global index enables fast data access. Upon registering a variable, the global index maps the variable key to a variable index (shown as vID in Figure 6). The variable index serves as a simplified key because a MemMan key can be a complex struct containing a string. When the variable is allocated on either CPU or GPU, an index of where the data is stored in the registry vector is added to the table. With the help of the global index class, a user can easily retrieve data from a known variable index.

3.2.3 Get context singleton. A unique pointer of the global registry is created to keep the scope of MemMan until its very last usage. We provide a `get_context_singleton` function that returns a static unique pointer to the global registry. All MemMan functions, including the bindings, interact with the same global registry object via the `get_context_singleton` function. The `get_context_singleton` function is hidden in the interface functions so the users do not use it directly, however it is an important function to guarantee that the memories will not be deallocated before the end of the program.

3.2.4 C interoperable layer. The C interoperable layer contains the interface functions that interact with the memory manager and can be accessed from Fortran via the `bind(c)` attribute. The C interoperable layer gets the unique pointer of the global registry and calls `register`, `allocate`, and `get` functions of MemMan with explicit template specification. The functions in the C interoperable layer are implemented in C++ and with the `extern "C"` keyword.

3.2.5 Fortran interface. The Fortran interface of MemMan provides intrinsic Fortran subroutine calls for `register`, `allocate`, and `get` data. One can also register and access GPU data from the Fortran interface of MemMan. The GPU backend is automatically determined during configuration. The Fortran interface accesses data on different GPUs by simply providing an index specifying the GPU to interact with.

logical type. The logical type is managed explicitly in MemMan. The logical type in Fortran does not have a standard size. Its sizes vary from 1, 2, 4, and 8 bytes. However, the C++ `bool` type is of size one byte. MemMan enforces all logical types in Fortran to be 1

```

main.f90
1 program main
2 use memman, only: var_descriptor, add_var_sp, allocate_var_sp
3 implicit none
4 integer :: ierr
5 interface
6 subroutine my_cpp_function() bind(c)
7 end subroutine
8 end interface
9 desc = var_descriptor("myvar", 0, 0, 0, 0)
10 ierr = add_var_sp(desc, [5, 5]) ! register a 5x5 single array
11 ierr = allocate_var_sp(desc) ! allocation
12 call my_cpp_function
13 end program

myfun.cpp
1 #include <memman/memman_cpp.hpp>
2 using namespace memman;
3 extern "C"{
4 void my_cpp_function() {
5     VarDescriptor desc = {"myvar", {0, 0, 0, 0}};
6     auto err_or_data = // access data
7     MemoryManager::find_data<schema::Array<schema::Float32>>(desc);
8     // use the err_or_data variant here
9 }
10 }

```

Figure 7: An example code snippet of allocating a CPU memory using MemMan Fortran interface and access the data in C++ code.

byte so that no data copies will be created, and the correct value will be passed and assigned.

3.2.6 GPU support. For GPU support, MemMan is tested to work with OpenACC, CUDA, and HIP frameworks. The GPU support works for the C++ backend and for the Fortran interface. MemMan also exposes the necessary primitives for data synchronization, tailored to the specific backend being used. MemMan can also be used with multiple GPUs, or with GPUs from different ecosystems at the same time.

4 MemMan Interface

MemMan provides very simple interfaces and the users can easily allocate and get data from Fortran and from C++. This section provides some code snippets of what MemMan looks like in the code. The examples uses the VarDescriptor that contains one string and four integers.

4.1 Call C++ from Fortran

Figure 7 shows an example code using MemMan to allocate a variable in Fortran and use it in C++. Line 10 in `main.f90` registers the variable and line 11 allocates the memory. The actual allocation is handled by the C++ backend via the Fortran interface. The data is only allocated when the allocation function is called. Therefore, users can still handle memory alignment using the Fortran interface, similar to what they would do with normal Fortran arrays.

Once the memory is allocated, users can access it in C++, as shown in line 6-7 in `myfun.cpp`. Compare to normal data allocation and access, MemMan only requires an extra line defining the

```

main.f90
1 program main
...
9 desc = var_descriptor("myvar", 0, 0, 0, 0)
10 device = mm_get_gpu_device_uid(0)
11 ierr = add_var_sp(desc, [5, 5]) ! register a 5x5 single array
12 ierr = allocate_var_sp(desc, device) ! allocation on GPU
...
14 end program

myfun.cpp
...
5 VarDescriptor desc = {"myvar", {0, 0, 0, 0}};
6 auto err_or_data = // access data
7 MemoryManager::find_data<schema::Array<schema::Float32>,
8 device::Cuda<0>>(desc);
...

```

Figure 8: An example code snippet of allocating a GPU memory using MemMan Fortran interface and access the data in C++ code. The repeating lines from Figure 7 are omitted.

variable key and one line getting the data before using it. However, MemMan saves the trouble of passing data pointer and sizes through the Fortran-C binding and the C-C++ binding. MemMan is much easier to use compare to C descriptors, and MemMan interoperates Fortran code directly to C++ while the C descriptors only binds to C.

MemMan can also handle calling C++-allocated data from Fortran. The interface namings are different in Fortran and in C++ because they are named in a way that our collaborator in the language is more comfortable with. However, the concepts for both Fortran and C++ interfaces in MemMan are the same. It takes one code line for each operation: variable registration, allocation, and data acquisition. A detailed document for the API and interfaces can be found online in the open-source repository.

4.2 Use GPU memory

Figure 8 shows the same example of Figure 7, but with Nvidia GPU memory. To allocate and get GPU memories with MemMan, one simply has to add a device argument in the function (Fortran) or in the template argument (C++). MemMan can handle memories on different GPUs by changing the device UID. Apart from Nvidia GPUs, MemMan also supports AMD GPUs, and can be extended to support other devices in the future. Details on how to use GPU memories in MemMan are also elaborated in the online document.

5 Benchmark

The MemMan library handles the data allocation and access from code written in Fortran and in C++. We show in this section that the overhead of data access is very small by benchmarking the MemMan operations. The benchmarks are run using Google Benchmark [7] and ForBenchmark [6] for C++ and Fortran codes, respectively. All benchmarks are compiled with the GNU compiler with -O3 optimization level and are run on a Dual Xeon Gold 6438Y CPU.

operation	Array size	#variables	time
Create MemMan	-	-	12.1 ns
Register variable	64	-	166 ns
	256	-	232 ns
	1024	-	458 ns
	4096	-	1212 ns
Allocate array	64	-	294 ns
	256	-	502 ns
	1024	-	721 ns
	4096	-	1239 ns
Get data by VarDescriptor	-	64	84.9 ns
	-	256	258 ns
	-	1024	968 ns
Get data by ID	-	64	39.3 ns
	-	256	39.3 ns
	-	1024	39.3 ns

Table 1: Operation benchmarks of MemMan.

5.1 Benchmark of operations in MemMan

Table 1 shows a table of benchmark results of the basic MemMan operations. The data registration and allocation are benchmarked with different array sizes because they are not affected by the number of variables. The `find_data` functions are benchmarked with different numbers of variables registered in MemMan because MemMan searches the inner table for the requested variable key. The `find_data` functions return the array pointer and therefore are not affected by its size. The benchmark result shows that all execution times of MemMan operations are small. `find_data` using the variable descriptor is comparable to the time of data allocation. Detailed benchmarks and a discussion of the `find_data` function continue in the next subsection.

5.2 Get data benchmark

The memories in MemMan can be accessed either by a known VarDescriptor or with the variable ID. The VarDescriptor is a key provided by the user, and the variable ID (vID) is the index generated by MemMan during variable registration. Using the VarDescriptor, the user would not need to pass any data between Fortran and C++. The user only needs a dummy C interface to call the C++ function from Fortran code. This solution is more flexible because one does not need to modify the interface to pass new arguments to the C++ function. On the other hand, the user can also pass the desired vIDs from Fortran to C++. Passing an integer per variable only requires minimal effort. The user does not need to handle the type conversions of different variables. The variable indexes provide fast access to variables in MemMan.

Figure 9 shows the benchmark result comparing `find_data` using VarDescriptor and vIDs. The worst time is the required time for accessing the last variable in the table. The average (avg) time is the time for the variable in the middle of the table. The data access time using vID does not grow with the number of registered variables because the memory position can be accessed directly

Figure 9: Benchmarks of data access time using the variable descriptor or the variable index. The red line is the number of global variables used in the ICON code base.

from the Global index table. On the other hand, data access time using VarDescriptors grows linearly with the number of registered variables.

We observe that the data access overhead is still very small (milliseconds) while given 1024 registered variables. As a reference, the climate and weather prediction model ICON, which has more than 2 million lines of code, uses fewer than 1000 global variables, shown in the graph with the red line. Even with the worst data access time using the variable descriptor, the data access time is still insignificant compared to the long simulation of ICON, which can easily take hours.

Data access via VarDescriptor in MemMan requires a small computational overhead, but provides easier cross-language code development. The user does not need to change the C interface of the function. One should choose whatever method best suits their application.

5.3 Variable key benchmark

The variable key for MemMan can be anything from an integer, a string, or even a struct containing multiple elements. By default, MemMan uses a var descriptor struct containing a string that represents the variable name and four indexes that describe either the physical position or time index of the variable. A complicated variable can help describe variables without manually repeating many similar name prefixes, such as `temperature_0`, `temperature_1`, etc.

Figure 10 shows the average data access time using different variable keys. We compare a simple key from an Integer to a complicated struct with the variable name (string) with different numbers of integers. We observe from the benchmark result that except for the integer key that shows better performance, the data access benchmarks of the structs that contain at least one string are similar. Despite having the best performance, using an integer as the key defeats the design of MemMan, which aims to provide easy access to variables. Requesting a variable by name, and not an integer, is more intuitive for code developers. We can also argue that adding

Figure 10: Benchmarks of data access time using the different variable keys.

integers to the variable key struct does not noticeably increase the data access time. The users can use the `VarDescriptor` struct as a key without a serious performance penalty compared to a variable name string.

From the benchmark results, we can see that data access is very small in general, but can still grow with the number of variables. For the ideal usage of `MemMan` in an application, one should register a variable in `MemMan` only when necessary. Variables that do not need cross-compile passing, such as local variables, should not be handled by `MemMan`. Secondly, the data access time is small but not costless. One should not repeatedly request the same data from `MemMan` over and over again. Each variable should be requested at the beginning of a function, and then reused inside the function. If data access is a huge performance concern for the user, one can still choose to pass variable indexes via the cross-compiling interface and access the variables using the efficient index access.

6 Application

In this section, we present usage examples for the `MemMan`.

6.1 Vector operation

Vector operations are one of the basic and most common operations for an application. In the numerical libraries, we often use the term `axy` to represent a basic vector operation $y = \alpha * x + y$. In this operation, x and y are vectors and α is a scalar.

Figure 11 reports the execution time of a Fortran main code performing `axy`, where array size of x and y are set to 1×10^7 . The figure compares 4 methods of implementing the same `axy` operation. Table 2 shows the implementation of each method that the figure compares. PETSc [13] and Ginkgo [10] are both numerical libraries. PETSc provides Fortran API, but Ginkgo only supports C++.

Each `axy` implementation is written in a function using either Fortran or C++, shown by the color of the bar. The `axy` functions are called and timed in the same Fortran driver. The memory

Method	Implementation
Fortran	$y = \alpha * x + y$
C++	<code>y[i] = alpha * x[i] + y[i]</code>
PETSc	<code>VecAXPY(y, alpha, x, ierr)</code>
Ginkgo	<code>y->add_scaled(alpha.get(), x.get())</code>

Table 2: Implementations for `axy` with different methods. Here x and y are arrays, and α is a scalar.

Figure 11: Axy performance comparison from a Fortran driver code using `MemMan` for cross-language implementation. The inset graph is a zoom in of the same result.

access of x , y , and α is managed by `MemMan`, and the data allocation/acquisition time is shown in red bars. This experiment is run only on the CPU.

From the results in Figure 11, we first see that the time for `MemMan` data accessing is small enough that it is almost negligible even for the simple `axy` operation. With the help of `MemMan`, we can implement independent `axy` functions in either Fortran and in C++, and call the functions from a Fortran driver code.

The figure shows that compilers does efficient optimizations to simple operations like `axy` such that basic implementations work better than calling operations from the numerical libraries. This result is reasonable because PETSc calls BLAS in the backend, and Ginkgo does not do specific optimization for CPU codes. The Fortran and C++ implementations can be further compared for different array sizes, shown in Figure 12.

In Figure 12, we compare `axy` operations with larger arrays. The result shows that, for smaller arrays, C++ outperforms Fortran. However, for arrays of size close to the integer limit, Fortran outperforms C++. Since both implementations are straightforward `axy` computations, the results show how the optimization of GNU compiler differs for Fortran and C++ languages.

This comparison is easily made possible using `MemMan` and without having to write two separate driver codes. Using the same driver code with the same timer also makes the comparison more

Figure 12: Axy performance comparison of Fortran and C++. The inset graph is a zoom in of the same result.

reliable. Note that as the array size grows, the MemMan data time becomes less significant compared to the actual computation.

6.2 Solving a linear system (CG)

The previous experiment shows that MemMan enables easy performance comparisons between Fortran and C++ implementations. However, the real value of MemMan lies when we have an expensive application in Fortran and we want to use numerical libraries that do not provide a Fortran API. Suppose that we have a sparse linear system $Ax = b$ in our application and we want to solve it with the conjugate gradient (CG) method [21].

CG is a powerful and widely used solver for solving linear systems. CG is an iterative Krylov subspace solver. It is time-consuming compared to simple vector or matrix operations. Luckily, CG has been implemented by Ginkgo and ported to different GPU ecosystems. We can write a small C++ function that gets data from the Fortran main code via MemMan, and then call the Ginkgo CG solver. Figure 13 shows how much performance we can gain by porting the CG solver to the Nvidia GPU. This example shows how MemMan can expand our options for improving code performance by introducing an interoperable Fortran and C++ memory manager.

7 Conclusion

This paper introduced a Fortran/C++ memory manager (MemMan) that handles data passing for cross-compiling codes. MemMan is a useful tool for binding Fortran and C++ code. Users interact with MemMan in Fortran and C++ separately for registering and getting variables. MemMan handles the data passing. The user does not need to handle the variable type or size matching. The benchmarks demonstrate that the MemMan incurs only minimal runtime

Figure 13: We can get significant performance improvement of a CG solver by using a C++ library that ports the computation to GPUs. The inset graph is a zoom in of the same result.

overhead for large codebases with hundreds of variables. One can use MemMan from a small performance comparison exercise to large-scale simulation models such as ICON.

MemMan manages data both in CPU and GPU memory, supporting different GPU vendors. MemMan can also handle memories on multiple GPUs, and GPUs of different vendors at the same time. The data handled by MemMan can be used in low-level GPU programming APIs such as CUDA and HIP, directive-based models such as OpenACC, and even performance-portable frameworks such as Kokkos. MemMan also provides Fortran programmers easy access to C++-only libraries such as Ginkgo and Eigen.

8 Future Work

Despite its useful features, MemMan has some limits. First, a pre-allocated Fortran array cannot be used in MemMan. The user always needs to modify the lines of code where their application allocates memory to use MemMan allocation in order to access the data from MemMan. The reason for the limit is that we choose not to use C descriptors. The issue can be revisited when the C descriptor feature in major compilers has become more robust. However, for memory safety reasons, the authors still recommend managing all memories in C++ if possible. As the example shows, one can manage memory alignment in Fortran code using the MemMan interface functions.

Secondly, MemMan currently only support basic data types such as integer types, floating point types, boolean, and the array of these types. MemMan is written flexibly enough to easily add more types. Types such as float16, bfloat16, or even posit can be considered. However, what types need to be implemented and how the Fortran interface interacts with the types require further research.

Similarly, MemMan can also support derived types. Adding a derived type and a corresponding struct in C++ is not difficult.

However, given the flexibility of derived types, it is impractical to implement all possibilities. How to automate adding a user-defined derived type to MemMan is yet to be investigated.

Lastly, MemMan only handles interoperability between Fortran and C++. A Python binding can be added to MemMan in the future to provide a more extensive support of language interoperability in HPC. A Python binding in MemMan is useful for interdisciplinary HPC and AI (Artificial Intelligence) research.

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